

Current Status of Human Resources at Commune Health Centers in Binh Duong Province According to National Standards for Commune Health and Factors Related to Public Satisfaction, 2023-2024

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ABSTRACT: The Vietnam National Standards for Commune Health through 2030 were established to reach a new milestone in primary healthcare for the population, in which developing the healthcare workforce is a critical condition for implementing professional activities. Aiming to describe the current status of the healthcare workforce at Commune Health Centers (CHCs) in Binh Duong Province, Vietnam, and its association with public satisfaction, a cross-sectional study was conducted across 91 CHCs with 336 residents in Binh Duong Province during 2023-2024. The results showed that the healthcare workforce met 98.9% of the requirements set by the National Standards for Commune Health through 2030; however, there was a shortage of nursing staff reaching 56.1%. Approximately 38.1% of residents believed that the current specialized workforce was insufficient to implement health activities. Residents' dissatisfaction regarding the centers' human resources was associated with regional factors and the use of preventive health services ($p < 0.05$). These findings suggest that health professional training should focus on nursing education, recruitment, and the deployment of additional nurses to Commune Health Centers.

KEYWORDS: Commune Health Centers, Binh Duong, healthcare workforce, National Standards for Commune Health, satisfaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

The new version of the National Standards for Commune Health in Vietnam, issued under Decision No. 1300/QĐ-BYT, emphasizes the pivotal role of human resources at Commune Health Centers (CHCs) in ensuring service quality and enhancing public satisfaction (1). Accordingly, each center must be staffed with an adequate number of doctors, nurses, midwives, and other essential personnel. This is necessary not only to fulfill the regulated technical service list but also to build trust and satisfaction within the community.

Shortages or imbalances in the workforce structure can lead to work overload, a decline in communication and service quality, and a reduction in public satisfaction—a crucial indicator of the effectiveness of the primary healthcare system (2). In the context of 2023, evaluating CHCs based on updated standards, particularly human resource criteria and public satisfaction with health services, is essential. This evaluation not only helps the health sector identify gaps for improvement but also serves as a foundation for budget allocation, professional support, and training programs tailored to the practical needs of Binh Duong Province.

The study was conducted with the following objectives:

- To describe the current status of the healthcare workforce at Commune Health Centers in Binh Duong Province in 2023, according to the National Standards for Commune Health.
- To assess the association between public satisfaction regarding human resources at Commune Health Centers in Binh Duong Province in 2024 and its related factors.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted from August 2022 to April 2025 in Binh Duong Province, Vietnam. The study subjects included all 91 Commune Health Centers (CHCs) in Binh Duong Province and 336 residents who had been living in the province for at least 12 months.

Current Status of Human Resources at Commune Health Centers in Binh Duong Province According to National Standards for Commune Health and Factors Related to Public Satisfaction, 2023-2024

Sampling Methods

- For Commune Health Centers: A total population sampling of all 91 centers was included in the study. Among these: 36 (39.6%) centers were in urban areas, 42 (46.2%) in peri-urban areas, and 13 (14.3%) in rural areas.

- For Residents: A multi-stage sampling technique was applied. Step 1: One commune-level unit was randomly selected to represent each of the 09 district-level localities. Step 2: One block or hamlet was then selected from each chosen commune. Step 3: A list of eligible residents from the selected blocks/hamlets was compiled; the sample size was calculated based on population proportions and a sampling interval $+k$. Step 4: A random starting point "a" was chosen, and subsequent participants were selected using the formula $a+k, a+2k$, etc until the required sample size was reached.

Data Collection and Analysis:

- Commune Health Centers: Evaluation was based on the scorecard for Criterion 2 – Healthcare Human Resources under Decision No. 1300/QĐ-BYT regarding the National Standards for Commune Health through 2030 (including staffing quantity, professional title structure, training, presence of doctors at the CHC, active trained village health workers, and implementation of policy regimes) (1) and Circular No. 03/2023/TT-BYT regarding job positions, staffing quotas, and professional title structures in public health units (doctors, nurses, midwives, other titles, and village health workers) (3).

- Residents: A satisfaction assessment tool regarding CHC human resources was utilized. This tool was adapted from a 2014 UNICEF and Ministry of Planning and Investment framework used in Dien Bien Province (4), with adjustments to align with current local scoring standards.

- Data Processing and Analysis: Data were processed using SPSS 29.0 software. Frequencies and percentages were used to describe qualitative variables. Odds Ratios (OR), 95% Confidence Intervals (CI), and p -values were calculated to determine univariate associations before being entered into a linear regression model for adjustment.

Ethical Considerations: The research objectives and content were thoroughly explained to all participants. Participation was voluntary and did not affect any CHC's performance evaluation or disciplinary actions, nor the personal lives of the residents. Data collection was approved by the leaders of the Binh Duong Provincial Health Department, and the identities of both individuals and Health Centers were kept strictly confidential.

3. RESEARCH CONTENT

3.1. Overview of Human Resource Standards for Commune Health Centers in Vietnam and Public Satisfaction

The standardization of human resources at Commune Health Centers (CHCs) in Vietnam is defined through legal documents and professional guidelines issued by the Ministry of Health. Specifically, Circular No. 03/2023/TT-BYT stipulates a minimum staffing quota of five personnel per CHC (1). Key positions include doctors/physician assistants, midwives, nurses, and other health titles aligned with the functions, tasks, and local demographic characteristics. Furthermore, adjustment coefficients based on geographic location and population size are applied to increase staffing levels where necessary. These regulations aim to ensure that CHCs possess the capacity to deliver primary healthcare services—ranging from basic medical examinations and treatments to prevention and community health education—in accordance with national plans to expand access to grassroots-level healthcare.

On the other hand, surveys regarding public satisfaction with primary healthcare services in Vietnam reveal a multidimensional perspective. Major studies utilizing data from the Vietnam Health Facilities Assessment indicate that patient satisfaction with basic services is influenced by factors such as waiting times, staff attitudes, and the quality of physical facilities (5, 6). Consequently, a segment of the population tends to bypass local centers in favor of higher-level facilities or private providers due to higher expectations for quality of care. This reflects a gap between regulated staffing standards and the actual service experience of the residents. It suggests that despite established personnel quotas, challenges remain in creating a primary healthcare experience that meets user expectations.

In summary, this overview indicates that strengthening the healthcare workforce while simultaneously improving communication skills, professional expertise, and the patient experience is pivotal. These elements are essential for achieving the Ministry of Health's goal of building an effective, people-friendly grassroots health system that plays a central role in community health care.

Current Status of Human Resources at Commune Health Centers in Binh Duong Province According to National Standards for Commune Health and Factors Related to Public Satisfaction, 2023-2024

3.2. Characteristics of Health Workforce and Public Satisfaction with Human Resources at Commune Health Centers in Binh Duong Province

Table 1. Distribution of Human Resources According to Circular 03/2023/TT-BYT (n = 91)

Characteristics		n	%
Doctors	On permanent payroll	80	87.9
	Seconded from higher levels	9	9.9
	None	2	2.2
Midwives	Yes	78	85.7
	No	13	14.3
Nurses	Yes	40	43.9
	No	51	56.1
Other Professional Titles	Yes	91	100.0
	No	0	0.0
CHCs with Full Village Health Worker Coverage	Yes	91	100.0
	No	0	0.0

Approximately 87.9% of Commune Health Centers (CHCs) have doctors on their permanent payroll, while 9.9% are supplemented by doctors seconded from higher-level facilities. This result shows a negligible difference compared to the 2022 report by the Binh Duong Provincial Health Department, which stated that 100% of CHCs had practicing doctors (7). Regarding other staff, 85.7% of centers have midwives, but only 43.9% have nurses. The workforce distribution shows that 70.3% are female; 56.4% hold intermediate vocational degrees, while those with bachelor's degrees account for 23.1%. The workforce is primarily concentrated in the medical specialty (56.4%), followed by pharmacy (21.8%). Consequently, the nursing shortage remains a critical issue that needs to be addressed at the CHCs.

The scoring results indicate that 78% of the stations meet the regional staffing requirements with a maximum score of 4 points; however, 19.8% only achieved between 3 and 3.5 points. This result likely aligns with the Binh Duong Provincial Health Department's reports regarding healthcare staff resignations following the COVID-19 pandemic. Although the situation has improved, it has yet to fully bridge the gap caused by the "brain drain" phenomenon in recent times. (7)

Furthermore, 87.9% of the centers achieved full points for the doctor criterion, as analyzed above. Regarding grassroots personnel, 80.2% of communes have health workers in every block or hamlet. The remaining 19.8% with incomplete coverage are also due to the pressures of the COVID-19 pandemic; additionally, it is challenging to mobilize volunteers for these roles as they are non-salaried positions that offer only a small allowance. Finally, 97.8% of the CHCs have fully implemented the state-mandated policies and benefit payments for both center staff and village health workers.

Table 2. Distribution of Healthcare Workforce by Academic Degree, Professional Title, and Gender

Characteristics		Total n (%)	Female n (%)	Male n (%)
Total		555 (100.0)	390 (70.3)	165 (29.7)
Education Level	Post-graduate	5 (0.9)	0 (0.0)	5 (100.0)
	Bachelor's degree	128 (23.1)	77 (60.2)	51 (39.8)
	Associate's degree	107 (19.3)	97 (90.7)	10 (9.3)
	Intermediate vocational	313 (56.4)	214 (68.4)	99 (31.6)
	Others	2 (0.4)	2 (100.0)	0 (0.0)
Professional Title	Medicine / Physician	313 (56.4)	254 (81.2)	59 (18.8)
	Pharmacy	121 (21.8)	65 (53.7)	56 (46.3)
	Nursing	40 (7.2)	20 (50.0)	20 (50.0)
	Technician	3 (0.5)	0 (0.0)	3 (100.0)
	Midwifery	78 (14.1)	75 (96.2)	3 (3.8)

The study results indicate that the healthcare workforce at Commune Health Centers is predominantly female (70.3%), with professional qualifications concentrated in the intermediate and associate degree groups (75.7%), while the proportion of staff with bachelor's degrees or higher remains low. This structure is consistent with the general characteristics of the primary healthcare system in Vietnam, where women dominate positions in primary care and preventive medicine. A World Health

Current Status of Human Resources at Commune Health Centers in Binh Duong Province According to National Standards for Commune Health and Factors Related to Public Satisfaction, 2023-2024

Organization (WHO) report on Vietnam's health workforce pointed out that women account for over 65% of the healthcare force, particularly at the grassroots level; however, limitations in advanced training opportunities and career development persist compared to their male counterparts (8). Simultaneously, the WHO emphasizes that the professional qualifications of grassroots health workers are a pivotal factor determining service delivery quality, especially in the context of rising non-communicable diseases and the demand for continuous community-based care (9).

Regarding professional titles, the proportion of physicians/doctors and midwives is high, whereas nurses account for only 7.2%, highlighting a significant imbalance in the workforce structure. This reality has also been documented in numerous studies across Vietnam, reflecting a nursing shortage at the primary healthcare level that affects the effectiveness of comprehensive care and chronic disease management (10, 11). Internationally, analyses from PubMed show that a balanced distribution among doctors, nurses, and midwives is closely linked to improved public health indicators, including reduced maternal and neonatal mortality and enhanced public satisfaction with primary health services (12). Therefore, these findings suggest an urgent need for strengthened training, standardized qualifications, and professional title restructuring at Commune Health Centers to meet the goal of Universal Health Coverage in Vietnam.

Table 3. Evaluation of Criterion 2 - Healthcare Human Resources according to the National Standards for Commune Health (n = 91)

Criterion 2 Components	Score (Points)	n	%
Ensure sufficient staffing and professional title structure according to the approved job position scheme; staff are trained and updated according to current regulations.	4.0 point	71	78.0
	3.5 point	3	3.3
	3.0 point	15	16.5
	2.0 point	2	2.2
	1.0 point and under	0	0.0
Availability of doctors working at the Commune Health Center.	2.0 points	87	95.6
	1.0 point	2	2.2
	0.0 points	2	2.2
Each block or hamlet has a trained and active village health worker.	2.0 points	73	80.2
	1.5 points	18	19.8
	1.0 point and under	0	0.0
Full implementation of state-mandated policies and benefits for center staff and village health workers.	2.0 points	89	97.8
	1.0 point	2	2.2
	0.0 points	0	0.0
Total Score for Criterion 2	Mean±SD	9.6 ± 0.6	
	Above 80%	90	98.9
	Below 80%	1	1.1

The total score for Criterion 2 shows that the average score achieved by Commune Health Centers (CHCs) in Binh Duong Province was 9.6 out of 10 points. Notably, 98.9% of the centers scored above 80% of the total points. A study by Nguyen Thi Thuy Duong in Hoa Binh (2018) indicated that public satisfaction increased 3.4 times when a doctor was stationed at the CHC (95% CI: 1.8 - 7.6) (6). The current findings show a slight decrease compared to 2022, when 100% of CHCs had a practicing doctor (with 67% on the permanent payroll), a midwife or a pediatric physician assistant, and 100% coverage of village health workers. These previous rates were achieved because district-level facilities implemented rotations and seconded doctors to work at CHCs in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic. Despite these shifts, the final result of 98.9% confirms that Criterion 2 regarding healthcare human resources remains maintained and ensured.

Table 4. Public Evaluation of Human Resources at Commune Health Centers (n = 336)

Characteristics	Contents	n	%
Perception of staffing levels at the Health Center	Insufficient / Too few	128	38.1
	Sufficient	174	51.8
	Excessive	10	3.0
	No opinion	24	7.2

Current Status of Human Resources at Commune Health Centers in Binh Duong Province According to National Standards for Commune Health and Factors Related to Public Satisfaction, 2023-2024

Characteristics	Contents	n	%
Attitude and conduct of healthcare staff	Very indifferent	3	0.9
	Indifferent	4	1.2
	Acceptable	62	18.5
	Attentive and thoughtful	184	54.8
	Very attentive and thoughtful	83	24.7
Evaluation of health activity implementation quality	Very poor	6	1.8
	Poor	6	1.8
	Average	70	20.8
	Good	192	57.1
	Very good	62	18.5

The study results show that more than half of the residents rated the staffing levels at Commune Health Centers as "sufficient" (51.8%). However, 38.1% still perceived a shortage of personnel, reflecting the widespread staffing pressures within the primary healthcare system. This finding aligns with WHO reports on primary healthcare, which emphasize that the shortage and inequitable distribution of the health workforce remain major barriers affecting service delivery and the quality of community-based primary care, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (13).

Regarding the attitude and conduct of healthcare staff, nearly 80% of residents provided ratings ranging from "acceptable" to "very attentive and thoughtful," indicating a relatively high level of satisfaction. This result is consistent with other studies in Vietnam, which record that the majority of patients are satisfied with the service attitude of grassroots health workers, despite existing limitations related to workload and working conditions (5, 14). International research also indicates that job satisfaction and a positive working environment for health workers are closely linked to the quality of communication and their attitude toward patients (15).

Evaluation of the quality of health activity implementation revealed that over 75% of residents rated it from "average" to "very good." This is in line with domestic studies on public satisfaction with public health services, where professional competence and service attitude are identified as the two decisive factors for overall satisfaction (5, 16). However, the significant proportion of residents perceiving a workforce shortage highlights the urgent need to continue strengthening and consolidating the primary healthcare workforce to maintain and enhance service quality amidst increasing healthcare demands.

Table 5. Association between Satisfaction with Healthcare Human Resources and Socio-demographic Factors and Service Utilization (n=336)

Characteristics		Satisfaction with Human Resources n (%)		Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p-value
		No	Yes		
Geographic Region	Region 1	112 (52.1)	103 (47.9)	1 (Ref)	
	Region 2	21 (52.5)	19 (47.5)	0.93 (0.45-1.93)	0.93
	Region 3	19 (23.5)	62 (76.5)	3.08 (1.62-5.86)	0.001
Income Group (Decision 59/2015/QD-TTg)	Groups 1-3	125 (43.6)	162 (56.4)	1 (Ref)	
	Groups 4-5	26 (55.1)	22 (44.9)	0.95 (0.48-1.90)	0.89
Primary Income Source	Agriculture	41 (48.8)	43 (51.2)	1 (Ref)	
	Business/Trade	111 (44.0)	141 (56.0)	1.25 (0.71-2.20)	0.43
Distance to Health Center	Under 1 km	42 (37.8)	69 (62.2)	1 (Ref)	
	1 km or more	110 (48.9)	115 (51.1)	0.67 (0.39-1.12)	0.13
Mode of Transportation	Non-motorized/Basic vehicle	21 (48.8)	22 (51.2)	1 (Ref)	
	Motorized vehicle (2-4 wheels)	131 (44.7)	162 (55.3)	1.05 (0.49-2.24)	0.88
	Under 30 minutes	135 (45.2)	164 (54.8)	1 (Ref)	

Current Status of Human Resources at Commune Health Centers in Binh Duong Province According to National Standards for Commune Health and Factors Related to Public Satisfaction, 2023-2024

Characteristics		Satisfaction with Human Resources n (%)		Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p-value
		No	Yes		
Travel Time to Health Center	30 minutes or more	17 (45.9)	20 (54.1)	1.30 (0.61-2.77)	0.49
Prenatal Care Services	Used	34 (31.5)	74 (68.5)	1 (Ref)	
	Not used	118 (51.8)	110 (48.2)	0.48 (0.26-0.89)	0.021
Childhood Immunization Services	Used	62 (43.1)	82 (56.9)	1 (Ref)	
	Not used	90 (46.9)	102 (53.1)	1.59 (0.93-2.74)	0.09
Health Communication Services	Used	115 (42.4)	156 (57.6)	1 (Ref)	
	Not used	37 (56.9)	28 (43.1)	1.17 (0.59-2.33)	0.65
Curative Care Services	Used	98 (41.2)	140 (58.8)	1 (Ref)	
	Not used	54 (55.1)	44 (44.9)	0.83 (0.48-1.43)	0.49
Preventive Health Services	Used	96 (39.2)	149 (60.8)	1 (Ref)	
	Not used	56 (61.5)	35 (38.5)	0.42 (0.23-0.77)	0.005

The resignation rate of the healthcare workforce in public facilities following the recent pandemic presents an extremely significant challenge, particularly as newly recruited staff are not yet experienced enough to immediately fill the void at the primary healthcare level (7). This concern is mirrored in a study by Xi Li et al. in China, a nation of over a billion people, which highlighted an increasing turnover rate among village doctors. This trend was attributed to factors such as burdensome clinical data archiving, inadequate financial subsidies, and a lack of incentives for cost-saving and operational efficiency improvements (17).

3.3. Measures to Enhance Public Satisfaction with Human Resources at Commune Health Centers

Based on the research findings, although most Commune Health Centers (CHCs) in Binh Duong Province met the human resource criteria of the National Standards (98.9% scored above 80%), 38.1% of residents still perceived staffing levels as insufficient—particularly in Region 1 and among frequent users of preventive services. To enhance public satisfaction, a synchronized set of solutions should be implemented:

First, strengthening and restructuring the workforce based on actual needs, with priority given to addressing the significant nursing shortage (only 43.9% of centers have nurses). A lack of nurses not only increases the workload for doctors and physician assistants but also directly impacts the patient experience in care, prevention, and primary health management. Therefore, plans for recruitment, rotation, or contract-based nursing additions are essential for high-volume centers, alongside optimized task delegation to mitigate the public perception of being "understaffed."

Second, maintaining a stable team of resident doctors at CHCs and reducing reliance on short-term secondments from higher levels. Evidence shows that the consistent presence of doctors at CHCs is vital for improving public satisfaction. Retention policies—such as improving working conditions, providing continuous training opportunities, and offering housing support or regional allowances—should be prioritized, especially given the post-COVID-19 trend of healthcare worker migration and resignations.

Third, enhancing communication skills and service quality to sustain the high satisfaction rates currently observed in staff conduct. While most residents rated staff as "attentive and thoughtful," long-term understaffing pressure could degrade communication quality. Integrating training programs on medical communication, patient-centered care, and effective time management is necessary for CHC staff.

Fourth, consolidating the network of village health workers, particularly in the 19.8% of localities with incomplete coverage. The higher satisfaction levels in Region 3 highlight the importance of service accessibility and the presence of health workers within the community. Adjusting allowances and motivation mechanisms is crucial to attract and retain these workers, thereby reducing the burden on CHCs.

Finally, proactively promoting preventive health services. The analysis indicated that users of preventive services had significantly lower levels of dissatisfaction. This suggests that regular access to preventive activities fosters a more positive

Current Status of Human Resources at Commune Health Centers in Binh Duong Province According to National Standards for Commune Health and Factors Related to Public Satisfaction, 2023-2024

evaluation of health personnel. Expanding and improving the quality of health education and preventive programs will contribute to both operational efficiency and community satisfaction.

4. CONCLUSION

The healthcare workforce at Commune Health Centers in Binh Duong Province in 2023 met 98.9% of the requirements set by the National Standards for Commune Health through 2030. However, a significant nursing shortage of 56.1% persists, and 38.1% of residents believe the current staffing is insufficient for operational needs. Dissatisfaction regarding human resources was found to be associated with regional factors and the utilization of preventive health services ($p < 0.05$). Health professional training should prioritize nursing education, alongside the strategic recruitment and deployment of additional nurses to Commune Health Centers.

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